

Metric-based Retargetability Assessment

Full set of questions

Luke Southall, luke.southall@student.kit.edu

Domenik Eichhorn, domenik.eichhorn@kit.edu

Joshua Ammermann, joshua.ammermann@kit.edu

Rinor Kelmendi, rinor.kelmendi@kit.edu

Prof. Dr. Ina Schaefer, ina.schaefer@kit.edu

1 Compilation Strategy Flexibility

1. **How much or how little control does a user have over compilation passes (selection, ordering, customization)?**
 - Very high control
 - Somewhat high control
 - Neutral
 - Somewhat low control
 - Very low control
2. **How extensive or limited are the pre-built compilation passes available for selection and configuration?**
 - Very extensive
 - Somewhat extensive
 - Neutral
 - Somewhat limited
 - Very limited
3. **How comprehensive or limited are the options for specifying and customizing hardware-specific constraints (e.g., qubit connectivity, gate fidelities)?**
 - Very comprehensive
 - Somewhat comprehensive
 - Neutral
 - Somewhat limited
 - Very limited

4. **How extensive or limited are the preset compilation strategies available (e.g., noise mitigation, depth reduction)?**
 - Very extensive
 - Somewhat extensive
 - Neutral
 - Somewhat limited
 - Very limited
5. **How robust or limited is the support for creating and integrating custom compilation passes?**
 - Very robust
 - Somewhat robust
 - Neutral
 - Somewhat limited
 - Very limited

2 Standardization Compliance

1. **How complete or incomplete is the compiler's support for QIR?**
 - Very complete
 - Somewhat complete
 - Neutral
 - Somewhat incomplete
 - Very incomplete
2. **How complete or incomplete is the compiler's support for OpenQASM (import and export)?**
 - Very complete
 - Somewhat complete
 - Neutral
 - Somewhat incomplete
 - Very incomplete

3. **How extensive or limited is the compiler's support for additional quantum-circuit description formats (e.g. Quil)?**
 - Very extensive
 - Somewhat extensive
 - Neutral
 - Somewhat limited
 - Very limited
4. **How active or inactive is the compiler's involvement in quantum-computing standardization efforts?**
 - Very active
 - Somewhat active
 - Neutral
 - Somewhat inactive
 - Very inactive
5. **How well or poorly does the compiler interoperate with other quantum frameworks (e.g., Cirq)?**
 - Very well
 - Somewhat well
 - Neutral
 - Somewhat poorly
 - Very poorly

3 Device-Agnostic Compiler Architecture

1. **How modular or monolithic is the compiler's overall architecture?**
 - Very modular
 - Somewhat modular
 - Neutral
 - Somewhat monolithic
 - Very monolithic
2. **How hardware-agnostic or hardware-specific are the compiler's components?**
 - Very hardware-agnostic
 - Somewhat hardware-agnostic
 - Neutral
 - Somewhat hardware-specific
 - Very hardware-specific

3. **How adaptable or limited is the compiler to diverse quantum gate sets?**
 - Very adaptable
 - Somewhat adaptable
 - Neutral
 - Somewhat limited
 - Very limited
4. **How high or low is the priority of hardware-agnostic design within the compiler?**
 - Very high priority
 - Somewhat high priority
 - Neutral
 - Somewhat low priority
 - Very low priority

4 Community and Ecosystem Integration

1. **How well or poorly integrated is the compiler with major and minor quantum-hardware providers?**
 - Very well integrated
 - Somewhat well integrated
 - Neutral
 - Somewhat poorly integrated
 - Very poorly integrated
2. **How strong or weak has the growth been in the number of supported backends over time?**
 - Very strong growth
 - Somewhat strong growth
 - Neutral
 - Somewhat weak growth
 - Very weak growth
3. **How extensive or limited are the compiler's extension capabilities (e.g., plugin system)?**
 - Very extensive
 - Somewhat extensive
 - Neutral
 - Somewhat limited
 - Very limited

4. **How easy or difficult is it to distribute a custom backend with the compiler?**

- Very easy
- Somewhat easy
- Neutral
- Somewhat difficult
- Very difficult

5. **How active or inactive is the community surrounding the compiler (e.g., commits, contributors, discussions)?**

- Very active
- Somewhat active
- Neutral
- Somewhat inactive
- Very inactive